

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

Programme	EU4HEALTH
Project number	101080009
Acronym	CAN.HEAL
Start Date	1 Nov 2022
Duration	30 months

Deliverable information

WP	9
Deliverable related number	D32
Deliverable number	D9.2
Deliverable name	Capacity Building
Deliverable Description	Results of NGS survey and capacity building precision oncology Electronic, English, 50 pages Online database
Lead Beneficiary	Jessa Hospital
Type	R
Dissemination level	PU
Version	03
Due Date	31/03/2025
Delivery Date	11/03/2025
Approval Date	

Revision History			
Version	Date	Comments	Partner
01	30/01/2025	Initial version: WP9 & WP10 capacity building report (Part 2)	Jessa Hospital, BE
02	02/03/2025	Integration of survey results (Part 1) in the deliverable report	Jessa Hospital, BE
03	11/03/2025	Final editing	Jessa Hospital, BE

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I. Part 1: Report on NGS Implementation in the EU – CAN.HEAL Survey Analysis

1. Introduction

The CAN.HEAL project aims to advance the integration of Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS) in cancer care across Europe by improving access to personalized medicine. To assess the current state of NGS implementation within the European Union (EU), a survey was conducted among various institutions to evaluate key aspects such as laboratory capacity, sequencing infrastructure, regulatory frameworks, reimbursement models, and clinical applications. The responses provide valuable insights into the degree of NGS adoption, highlighting variations at national, regional, and institutional levels. This report presents an analysis of the survey findings, focusing on the challenges and disparities in NGS availability, reimbursement, and standardization. The results serve as a basis for identifying gaps and recommending strategies to optimize the equitable implementation of NGS across Europe.

2. Methodology

The survey aimed to map current practices regarding NGS activities, Molecular Tumor Boards (MTB), Decision Support Tools (DST), and regulatory, economic, and healthcare policy aspects of NGS. The survey questions were collaboratively designed and agreed upon by the leads of Work Packages (WP) 8, 9, and 10 of the CAN.HEAL consortium to ensure relevance to key aspects of NGS implementation across Europe (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Survey structure and collaboration framework within CAN.HEAL for the mapping of NGS and MTB activities and the use of DSTs through an EU-wide survey.

This survey was conducted using Microsoft Forms as a digital platform for data collection.

This report covers the results of the survey on NGS activities, and regulatory, economic, and healthcare policy aspects of NGS. The survey results on MTB and DST are reported in the CAN.HEAL deliverable reports of WP8 and WP10¹ respectively.

Target audience and data collection

The survey targeted all CAN.HEAL consortium partners, each with expertise in at least one relevant aspect of its scope. Additionally, consortium partners were encouraged to share the survey invitation with their professional networks. By leveraging these networks, the survey aimed to capture a broad and diverse representation of NGS, MTB and DST activities across multiple European countries.

However, this approach introduces a potential selection bias. Since the CAN.HEAL partners are often engaged in advanced precision medicine initiatives, their responses may not fully reflect the broader landscape of NGS implementation across Europe, particularly in institutions with more limited sequencing capacity or less involvement in large scale initiatives such as CAN.HEAL.

The survey adhered to General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) guidelines, ensuring that responses were collected, processed, and stored in compliance with EU data protection laws. No personally identifiable information was shared, and data handling followed strict confidentiality measures.

Limitations of the survey

While the survey provides valuable insights into NGS activities, several limitations must be acknowledged:

Incomplete coverage of EU NGS activity: The extent of total NGS activity in the EU covered by this survey is unknown. The sample is not exhaustive, and it remains unclear how the missing institutions might influence the overall interpretation of the results. Some major sequencing centers may not be represented, potentially skewing the findings.

Reliability of self-reported data: The survey relies entirely on self-reported data from participating institutions. While respondents were expected to provide accurate information, inconsistencies in interpretation, data reporting errors, or knowledge gaps could affect the reliability of responses.

Lack of standardized verification: The data provided could not be independently verified against external sources. Differences in institutional record-keeping and subjective interpretations of certain questions may introduce variation in response accuracy.

¹ CAN.HEAL D10.1: [D10.1 EU-oncDST](#)

Despite these limitations, this survey provides a valuable overview of NGS practices in Europe. While the results may not represent the full spectrum of NGS activity across all EU countries and institutions, they highlight important trends, disparities, and areas for potential improvement. Future studies could aim for a more comprehensive and representative dataset, incorporating responses from a wider range of institutions and validating self-reported data with independent metrics where possible.

3. Survey Findings

A. Characteristics of the respondents

The survey respondents represent a diverse range of institutes across Europe, reflecting various roles, experience levels, and areas of specialization within the field of Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) and precision oncology.

In total, 117 respondents answered the full survey, from 93 different institutes, in 17 countries.

For the purpose of this report, covering the NGS activity section, the answers of 64 respondents were taken into account.

Figure 2: Geographic distribution of the institutes of the respondents

The respondents come from institutes spread across multiple European countries (Figure 2), ensuring broad representation of NGS activities within the EU. This distribution allows for

comparative insights into how NGS is implemented in different healthcare systems and regulatory environments.

The survey captured input from professionals in diverse roles within their respective institutions (Figure 3). The respondents were mainly molecular biologists (46.9 %), physicians specialized in laboratory medicine (21.9 %; pathologists, clinical geneticists, clinical biologists, a.o.) and clinicians (20.3%; oncologists and haemato-oncologists). This range of expertise provides a broad perspective on the challenges and opportunities associated with NGS activity in clinical settings.

Figure 3: Role distribution of the respondents

Respondents also vary in their level of experience in the field, spanning from early-career professionals to highly experienced experts with many years of practice (Figure 4). Professionals with > 12 years of experience represented the majority of respondents (59.4 %), ensuring insights from professionals who have observed the evolution of NGS technologies over time.

Figure 4: Distribution of the experience of the respondents in years.

The majority of respondents are involved in solid tumor analysis (84.4%), with a slightly lower proportion engaged in haemato-oncology (70.3%). More than half (54.7%) work in both areas. Pediatric oncology is represented by a smaller fraction of respondents (31.2%), likely reflecting the lower prevalence of cancer in children compared to adults.

Figure 5: Distribution of the area of involvement of the respondents, left: solid tumors versus haematological neoplasms; right: pediatric versus adult oncology.

Overall, the characteristics of the survey respondents indicate a well-balanced representation of European professionals involved in NGS. The inclusion of professionals from various roles, experience levels, and specialties enhances the validity of the survey findings, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of NGS implementation across Europe.

B. Size of sequencing facilities

Variability in sample throughput

The survey revealed substantial variations in the number of samples processed per year by different institutions (Figure 6). While some large institutes handle more than 2000 samples annually (23.4%), the majority of institutes process fewer than 1000 samples per year (57.8 %) with 32.8 % of institutes processing < 500 samples per year. Two institutes, both in Italy, handle < 100 samples per year.

Even within specific countries, major differences exist. For example, in Italy, France, Belgium and Spain, countries with highly developed healthcare systems, some institutions reported high sample volumes, while others have significantly lower throughput. It is noteworthy that the single Slovenian institute represented in the Survey is a high-volume institute with > 2000 samples per year. In Belgium, in contrast to most other countries, more responding institutes have > 1000 samples/year (n=4) versus < 1000 samples (n=2).

This variation suggests a partial and variable degree of centralization in NGS activities, where certain institutions handle a larger share of sequencing, while others engage in it to a more limited extent.

Figure 6: Samples per year across institutes

Variability in number of sequencing instruments

The number of sequencers available per institution also varies widely (Figure 7). While some institutions possess > 5 sequencing instruments (16.0 %), the majority of institutes operate with three or less instruments (52.3 %). A significant portion (9.5 %) reports having only a single machine.

In most countries, the majority of institutions operate with 1 to 5 sequencers (DE: 80 %; IT: 82 %; FR: 93 %; ES: 100 %), while none or only one or two institutes have 5 instruments.

Belgium, however, stands out with an unusual distribution: of 6 institutes, half have more than 5 sequencing instruments. This is striking given Belgium’s relatively small size compared to other countries with fewer high-capacity centers.

A limitation of this analysis is that it does not account for sequencer throughput; fewer high-capacity machines may outperform multiple smaller ones. This may explain why some institutes handle > 2000 samples with 4 instruments (f.i. SI01, GR02) while other institutes with 4 instruments handle less than 1.000 samples (f.i. DE02, IT02).

Figure 7: Number of sequencers per institute

Variability in number of NGS panels of applications

The variability in size and throughput of the institutes is also reflected in the number of NGS applications (Figure 8), both across the EU and within single countries. 45 % of institutes offer 1 to 3 different NGS applications while 55 % offer 4 or more applications. In Belgium and Italy, the majority of institutes (> 50 %) offer more than 5 NGS applications.

Figure 8: Number of NGS panels or applications per institute

To conclude, the survey highlights significant variability in the size, throughput, and application range of NGS laboratories across Europe.

This variation suggests an uneven and partially centralized NGS landscape, where a few high-volume institutes dominate sequencing activities, while many operate on a smaller scale. Differences in efficiency, resource allocation, and institutional focus likely contribute to these disparities.

Overall, these findings indicate that NGS implementation across Europe lacks uniformity, with structural and operational differences that might affect access to sequencing services. Addressing these disparities, whether through investment in infrastructure, optimization of workflows, or fostering collaboration between high- and low-volume centers, could help create a more balanced and efficient NGS landscape.

C. NGS advancement across the EU

The survey provides insights into the extent of NGS adoption across European institutes, focusing on the size of sequencing panels used and how Whole-Genome Sequencing (WGS), Whole-Exome Sequencing (WES), or Comprehensive Genomic Profiling (CGP) are applied in clinical practice.

NGS panel size across institutes

Figure 9 depicts the most advanced NGS panel or application being used by the institute. It highlights that many institutions (25%) use large NGS panels covering 100-500 genes. However, a significant number of institutions still rely on small gene panels (0-100 genes) (31.3%).

Figure 9: Size of the most advanced NGS application available at institute.

WES is used by 18.8% of institutes, indicating that a significant proportion of institutions have moved beyond gene panels to broader genomic profiling. WGS remains relatively rare (4.7%), only available in 3 institutes in the Netherlands, Italy and France.

The variability in NGS panel size is also evident at the country level. Countries like Italy and France are represented in the whole spectrum of NGS panel sizes, including WES and WGS. At the contrary, Spain and Belgium do not have WES and WGS institutes, suggesting a slower integration of these high-throughput sequencing technologies in these countries. Poland and Slovenia, however, have WES available, with all four Polish institutes relying on large panels (>500 genes) or WES, highlighting a strong commitment to broader genomic profiling. Portugal and Malta, each represented by a single surveyed institute, report less advanced NGS applications, suggesting a more limited scope of genomic sequencing in these regions.

Use of WGS, WES, or CGP in clinical practice

Figure 10 assesses the extent to which WGS, WES, or CGP are used in diagnostics, categorized from "not used" (1) to "standard method in all tumor types" (5).

Figure 10: extent of use of CGP, WES and/or WGS, 1 = Not used, 2 = In specific tumor types, if reimbursed, 3 = On a case by case basis, specifically requested by a local oncologist, 4 = In specific tumor types, agreed upon by (local, national or international) experts, 5 = Used in all tumor types as standard method.

34.4% of institutes (n=22) do not use WGS, WES, or CGP. This confirms that a substantial portion of European institutions still rely on smaller targeted panels for routine diagnostics.

Only 6.2% of institutes (n=4) use these methods as a standard approach across all tumor types, indicating that comprehensive genomic profiling is not yet widely integrated into routine oncology practice.

28.1% (n=18) use these methods selectively in specific tumor types, based on expert consensus. This highlights that some institutes follow structured guidelines for comprehensive sequencing but do not apply it broadly.

Use of composite or complex biomarkers

Figure 11 illustrates the adoption of advanced molecular biomarkers in clinical and research settings across different European institutes. It highlights the use of Homologous Recombination Deficiency (HRD), Methyloomics, Microsatellite Instability (MSI), Transcriptomics, and Tumor Mutational Burden (TMB) and also shows the proportion of institutions that do not use any of these biomarkers.

MSI (27.0%) is the most frequently analyzed composite biomarker using NGS. As a well-established predictive marker for immunotherapy response, its use is widespread and growing. However, its relatively moderate adoption in NGS-based analysis is likely due to the continued reliance on alternative techniques, such as Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) and immunohistochemistry (IHC), which are more commonly used to determine MSI status in clinical practice.

Figure 11: use of composite or complex biomarkers across the EU. HRD: Homologous Recombination Deficiency; MSI: Microsatellite Instability; TMB: Tumor Mutational Burden

Although HRD testing is essential for PARP inhibitor eligibility, particularly in high-grade serous ovarian carcinoma, only 24.1% of institutes perform it. Its limited adoption likely stems from restricted reimbursement indications and the technical complexity of analysis, which requires genomic instability scoring and copy number alterations. Wider adoption may follow as clinical applications expand and reimbursement policies evolve.

TMB is increasingly explored for immunotherapy decision-making, but its adoption remains inconsistent across countries, with only 23.4% of institutes analyzing it. Unlike MSI, TMB is not included in any clinical guidelines or drug labels, which likely limits its routine implementation.

Transcriptomics (9.9%) and Methylomics (2.8%) have the lowest adoption rates, likely due to their higher costs, technical complexity, and lack of established clinical guidelines. These approaches are primarily used in translational or clinical research projects rather than routine clinical practice, reflecting their emerging role in precision oncology rather than widespread diagnostic implementation.

A notable minority (8.5%) of institutes do not use any of these biomarkers, indicating gaps in biomarker adoption and potential limitations in sequencing infrastructure, expertise, or funding.

Adoption of NGS on ‘liquid biopsy’

Figure 12 shows that NGS on liquid biopsy is in varying stages of adoption across Europe.

Figure 12: adoption phase of NGS on liquid biopsy.

While many institutes are in the testing phase or clinical trials, a significant number are planning to set up, indicating growing interest. However, some institutes have no plans to implement it, which might be due to financial or regulatory barriers or institutional expertise or focus. Only a smaller group has fully integrated liquid biopsy NGS into routine clinical care.

At the country level, countries like Belgium, The Netherlands and Italy have a broader implementation rate compared to other countries.

Expanding on the current and planned applications of NGS on liquid biopsy (data not shown), the primary and most advanced use is as a substitute for tumor tissue in tumor profiling and treatment selection (n=45), highlighting its established role in clinical oncology where tissue sampling is difficult or unavailable. Seventeen respondents report using liquid biopsy NGS for minimal residual disease (MRD) detection, indicating a growing but still evolving role in disease monitoring and relapse prediction. Primary cancer screening, reported by six institutes, remains in the early stages of adoption, likely due to technological challenges and ongoing validation requirements, regulatory constraints, and the need for stronger clinical evidence. These findings suggest that while liquid biopsy is increasingly integrated into diagnostics and monitoring, its broader applications, such as early detection, are still emerging and require further clinical validation and standardization.

Paired tumor-normal sequencing

Sequencing normal DNA alongside tumor DNA, in order to distinguish germline variants from somatic variants and to identify hereditary germline variants associated with increased (familial) cancer risk is performed by a minority of institutes (34.4 %) (data not shown). Whether an incidental finding of a potential germline variant identified by tumor-only sequencing leads to appropriate follow-up was not questioned in the survey.

In conclusion, most European institutes rely on (small panel) targeted sequencing, while WES and WGS remain limited. Comprehensive sequencing (WGS, WES, CGP) is not yet widely adopted as a routine diagnostic tool, with most institutions using it only in specific tumor types or on a case-by-case basis. Limited reimbursement and cost constraints are likely major barriers, as many institutes use WGS, WES, or CGP only when reimbursed or selectively in specific tumor types. Although MSI and HRD are analyzed more frequently than other biomarkers, their adoption is still far from universal, likely due to alternative testing methods and/or restricted indications and reimbursement challenges. While TMB is not yet included in clinical guidelines or drug labels, a notable number of institutes do analyze it, suggesting ongoing interest in its potential clinical relevance. Transcriptomics (9.9%) and Methyloomics (2.8%) show very low adoption rates, likely remaining largely confined to research rather than clinical practice. Similarly, NGS on liquid biopsy is primarily used as an alternative to tissue-based testing for tumor profiling, with growing but still limited applications in minimal residual disease monitoring, and early cancer detection, highlighting the need for further clinical validation and broader implementation.

D. Turnaround time and Quality Assessment

Figure 13 summarizes the turnaround times (TAT) for the different NGS applications as reported by the respondents. It shows significant variability for different NGS applications across European institutes, with targeted DNA and RNA sequencing generally being the fastest and WGS and WES requiring considerably more time.

Figure 13: Turnaround times of different NGS applications across the institutes of the EU

Many institutes complete targeted sequencing within 5-10 days, although an equal number exceeds 15 days. WGS and WES exceed 15 or 20 days in all institutes. CGP, with turnaround times closer to targeted panels, is generally faster than WGS and WES, making it a more practical option for clinical decision-making. Although CGP provides comprehensive genomic insights, it remains more targeted and streamlined, allowing for faster processing and interpretation. To enable WGS and WES for routine diagnostics, bioinformatics optimization, automation, and workflow improvements are needed to accelerate data analysis and reduce turnaround times.

Figure 14 illustrates the accreditation status of the surveyed institutes, indicating whether they hold certification under a recognized quality standard, such as ISO 15189 for medical laboratories. The majority of institutes (60.9%) are already accredited, while an additional 21.9% are in the process of obtaining accreditation. In Belgium, Germany, and the Netherlands, where multiple institutes participated in the survey, all institutes are accredited, reflecting strong regulatory compliance and quality assurance frameworks. In contrast, accreditation status is more variable in other countries.

Figure 14: accreditation status of the surveyed institutes

Figure 15 shows that 7.8% of institutes also do not participate in external quality assessments (EQA), suggesting potential areas for quality improvement. Additionally, 29.7% of institutes participate in EQC as a mandatory requirement in their country. In Belgium, EQA participation

seems to be consistently mandatory, while in countries like France, Italy, and Germany, regional differences appear, suggesting variability in regional regulatory enforcement of quality standards.

Figure 15: participation in external quality assessments (EQA)

E. NGS bioinformatics aspects

The survey results on NGS bioinformatics practices are all represented in ANNEX 1. These results show substantial variability and a lack of standardization across multiple aspects of data processing, analysis pipelines, variant interpretation, and infrastructure. This heterogeneity might impact the reproducibility, interoperability, and clinical reliability of NGS-based diagnostics.

One of the most striking findings is the diverse range of bioinformatics pipelines and tools used across institutes, with no universally adopted standards. While some institutes rely on commercial

software with predefined workflows, others use custom-built or open-source pipelines. The choice of reference genomes, alignment tools, and variant filtering criteria further varies, complicating cross-institutional data comparison and standardization efforts.

Moreover, quality control metrics are variable raising concerns about data reliability, particularly for clinical applications, where accurate variant detection is critical for patient management. Additionally, the use of computational infrastructure is highly diverse, ranging from locally secured servers and external hard drives to cloud-based solutions, each presenting unique challenges in terms of data security, scalability, and compliance with GDPR and other regulatory frameworks.

The interpretation of variant pathogenicity and clinical relevance also lacks uniformity. Different institutes apply varied guidelines, scoring systems, and databases, leading to potential discrepancies in clinical reporting and decision-making.

Additionally, data storage, sharing, and reanalysis policies show major disparities, with some institutes maintaining long-term archiving and data-sharing agreements, while others face limitations possibly due to storage capacity, costs, or regulatory restrictions. This fragmentation hinders collaborative research, cross-border data integration, and retrospective analyses.

These findings highlight a critical need for standardization in NGS bioinformatics workflows across Europe. Establishing harmonized protocols for variant calling, QC, data interpretation, and reporting is essential to ensure data comparability, clinical reliability, and regulatory compliance. Greater investment in shared infrastructure, standardized training programs, and bioinformatics accreditation frameworks could significantly improve the consistency, accuracy, and scalability of NGS bioinformatics in clinical settings across the EU.

F. Reimbursement status of different NGS applications

Figure 16 illustrates the reimbursement status of different NGS applications as answered by all the NGS laboratory respondents. The figure shows variable reimbursement across NGS applications, with targeted DNA NGS most commonly covered, while WES, WGS, and RNA sequencing, face more restrictions. Liquid biopsy NGS and CGP have moderate reimbursement. When reimbursed, it is mainly limited to selected tumor types, likely based on specific guidelines. NGS data reanalysis and separate bioinformatics evaluations are rarely funded, limiting reuse for refined interpretations. The findings suggest that only well-established NGS applications receive routine reimbursement, while broader genomic approaches remain financially constrained. A more in-depth analysis of the regulatory and financial aspects of NGS was explored in a subsequent section of the survey, with the results presented in the following paragraphs.

Figure 16: reimbursement status of NGS applications

G. Regulatory and financial aspects

Respondents from 20 institutes indicated that they were sufficiently aware of regulatory and financial aspects of NGS organization and reimbursement and provided responses on these topics. Nineteen institutes reported the existence of a regulatory framework or initiative supporting NGS, either at the regional (n=4) or national level (n=15) (data not shown).

Regarding the centralization of NGS testing, 8 out of 20 respondents (40%) stated that testing is restricted to a limited number of recognized laboratories (Figure 17), while none reported centralization within academic centers. Notably, 7 of these 8 institutes indicated that this centralization is driven by a governmental strategy (data not shown).

Figure 17: Centralization of NGS in the country or region.

When asked about NGS reimbursement in their country or region, 3 respondents (15%) reported that NGS is not reimbursed (Figure 17), and that NGS is paid for by either the hospital (n=3) and/or the patient (n=1) (data not shown). The majority however confirmed reimbursement through either regular healthcare funding (50%) or extraordinary funding mechanisms (35%) (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Reimbursement of NGS

The surveyed modalities of NGS reimbursement are summarized in Figure 19, illustrating significant variability in NGS reimbursement modalities across Europe, with differences in guideline-based, disease stage-dependent, trajectory phase-dependent, and testing strategy-dependent reimbursement models.

Figure 19: modalities of NGS reimbursement.

Nearly half (47.1%) of respondents indicated that NGS reimbursement follows national or regional guidelines, while a smaller proportion (29.4%) follows European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) recommendations, and 11.8% reported no guideline-based reimbursement at all. In terms of disease stage, 64.7% reported coverage across all stages, whereas 35.3% stated that reimbursement is limited to locally advanced or metastatic disease. Patient's trajectory phase-dependent reimbursement also varies, with only 29.4% reporting unrestricted reimbursement, while the rest face limitations such as once-per-year coverage (23.5%) or only when standard-of-care options are exhausted (17.6%). Finally, testing strategy-dependent reimbursement shows that while 66.7% have upfront reimbursement for any NGS panel size, others follow a sequential approach, where RNA NGS is reimbursed only if DNA NGS is negative (22.2%), or small NGS panels must precede larger panels (11.1%). These findings highlight the fragmented reimbursement landscape for NGS in Europe, which may impact equitable access to precision oncology.

Furthermore, the survey results highlight significant variability in the presence of policies for the combined reimbursement of newly approved drugs and their corresponding biomarker NGS testing across European institutes (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Governmental strategy for the combined reimbursement of newly approved drugs and corresponding biomarker testing by NGS

Nearly half of respondents (47.4%) stated that a policy exists but with suboptimal results, suggesting that while frameworks are in place, they may be ineffective, possibly due to delays, insufficient budget, or administrative challenges. Meanwhile, 26.3% reported that no such policy exists, indicating a lack of integration between biomarker testing and drug reimbursement in

several countries or regions, which could delay access to precision oncology treatments. Additionally, 21.1% answered "I don't know," reflecting either a lack of awareness or unclear national policies, underscoring the need for greater transparency and communication regarding reimbursement systems. Only one respondent (5.3%) reported a successful policy (Slovenia), suggesting that efficient models for aligning drug and biomarker test reimbursement remain rare in Europe.

These findings indicate that several European healthcare systems struggle to synchronize biomarker testing with drug reimbursement, potentially delaying patient access to targeted therapies. To improve implementation, countries should consider more streamlined and proactive policies that ensure biomarker tests are reimbursed in parallel with the approval of corresponding therapies, reducing treatment delays and enhancing the impact of precision medicine.

On the question whether NGS can be requested and performed with the specific objective of testing patient's eligibility for a biomarker driven clinical trial, 17 of 20 institutes answers yes. In only 3 of these (SL01, NO01, FR11), the NGS testing is reimbursed. In the remaining 14, the NGS is paid for by pharmaceutical companies (n=7), the laboratory of hospital (n=7) and/or the patient (n=2) (data not shown).

Related to these questions was the question on whether there are ongoing initiatives to negotiate NGS reimbursement (e.g. new or improved) (Figure 21). The results show variable stakeholder involvement in NGS reimbursement negotiations across Europe.

Figure 21: Ongoing initiatives for negotiating new or improved NGS reimbursement.

While 35.0% report joint efforts by clinicians and NGS laboratories, 20.0% indicate authority-led initiatives, and smaller shares involve NGS laboratories (10.0%) or clinicians alone (5.0%). Meanwhile, 15.0% report no active initiatives, highlighting regional disparities. These findings suggest a fragmented approach and emphasize the need for stronger collaboration between authorities, laboratories, and clinicians to improve NGS access.

Figure 22 illustrates the variability in reimbursement rates for NGS testing across European institutes, with respondents able to provide multiple answers to account for different panel sizes and applications. Reimbursement rates are highly diverse, ranging from less than €300 to over €2.100, likely reflecting differences in national policies, panel complexity (e.g. small versus WES/WGS), and healthcare system budgets. The most common reimbursement range is 900 - 1.200€ (29.6%). Several institutes report 300 - 600€ (25.9%) or even lower reimbursements (< €300, 3.7%), suggesting that in some countries or regions, NGS remains underfunded. A smaller proportion of respondents reported higher rates exceeding 1.200, 1.500 or 2.100€ suggesting that some institutes are selectively well-compensated. The findings highlight the fragmented nature of NGS reimbursement across Europe.

Figure 22: NGS reimbursement rates.

Figure 23 illustrates whether reimbursement rates sufficiently cover NGS expenses, providing insight into the financial sustainability of NGS testing across European institutes. Notably, more respondents answered this question than the previous one, which is unexpected. Nearly half of the institutes report financial losses, either significant (25.9%) or minor (20.4%), highlighting ongoing funding challenges. When combined with Figure 21, a pattern emerges: institutes

receiving lower reimbursement rates (\leq €600) are more likely to report financial shortfalls, suggesting that current funding levels may be inadequate. The fragmented reimbursement landscape across Europe indicates that while some regions or countries offer more sustainable funding, others risk underfunding, potentially limiting access to NGS and its clinical implementation. Better alignment between reimbursement rates and actual NGS costs is crucial to ensure long-term sustainability and equitable access to precision medicine.

Figure 23: Do the NGS reimbursement rates cover the NGS expenses?

H. Opinions on the use of NGS in clinical practice

To conclude the survey, all respondents were asked to provide their opinions on various aspects of NGS implementation, challenges, and accessibility (Figure 24). The results highlight widespread agreement on the increasing need for NGS testing (98%) and the necessity for additional funding, particularly for education (94%) and data storage (93%), indicating that financial and infrastructure support remain key concerns. Reimbursement for data analysis, interpretation, and reporting is widely considered insufficient (87%), emphasizing the need for better compensation of NGS post-analytics.

Despite recognizing NGS as a technology improving lab-efficiency (85%), 78% believe there is still room for improvement in their institution or country. Societal costs, including equipment and IT infrastructure, are considered a major barrier for 67% of respondents, while only 65% feel there is sufficient local expertise to support NGS testing, suggesting workforce and training gaps.

Figure 24: Opinions of all survey respondents on topics related to NGS

On the clinical impact side, 59% of respondents agree that suboptimal NGS access leads to suboptimal patient treatment, while turnaround time satisfaction remains mixed (59%), indicating room for workflow optimization. Over half (52%) report resorting to cheaper alternatives due to

high NGS costs, and 57% feel access is not equitable across their country or region, raising concerns about disparities in availability.

Finally, stakeholder awareness remains an issue, with 65% believing that payers are not fully aware of the complexity and costs of NGS, and 50% stating that patients are not well informed about NGS, highlighting the need for better education and communication at both policy and patient levels. These results underscore the financial, logistical, and educational challenges that must be addressed to ensure equitable and efficient implementation of NGS across Europe.

4. Conclusion

The survey highlights significant variability in NGS implementation across Europe, reflecting differences in infrastructure, clinical application, bioinformatics practices, regulatory frameworks, and reimbursement policies. While targeted small-panel sequencing is widely used, more comprehensive approaches like Comprehensive Genomic Profiling (CGP), Whole-Exome Sequencing (WES), Whole-Genome Sequencing (WGS), remain moderate or limited and inconsistently adopted. The lack of harmonized protocols, standardized bioinformatics workflows, and equitable reimbursement policies presents major challenges for the integration of NGS into routine clinical practice.

One of the major barriers identified is reimbursement, which is fragmented across Europe. While some institutions receive reasonable compensation for NGS tests, others report insufficient funding, particularly when reimbursement is below €600, leading to financial losses for laboratories. Additionally, combined reimbursement policies for newly approved drugs and associated biomarker testing are often ineffective or absent, potentially delaying access to precision therapies. Financial strain on laboratories may limit patient access to advanced genomic testing. Additionally, stakeholder awareness remains low, with many respondents indicating that payers and policymakers underestimate the complexity and cost of NGS implementation.

Turnaround times (TATs) also vary widely, with targeted DNA and RNA sequencing being the fastest, while WES and WGS often exceed 15-20 days, making them presently less practical for timely clinical decision-making.

The survey also underscores the need for improved quality assurance and standardization. While a majority of institutes are accredited or in the process of accreditation, participation in external quality assessment (EQA) programs is inconsistent, which may impact data reliability and reproducibility. The lack of standardized bioinformatics workflows and data-sharing frameworks, widely recognized as underfunded and requiring better reimbursement, further complicates cross-border collaboration and interoperability in precision oncology. Furthermore, despite the

increasing need for NGS, concerns remain regarding societal costs, lack of local expertise, and inequitable access to testing.

I. Recommendations for the European Commission

To enhance the equitable adoption of NGS across Europe, the following key actions are recommended based on the findings of this large-scale survey across the EU:

Harmonize NGS reimbursement policies and regulatory frameworks

- ✓ Develop EU-wide guidelines to ensure reimbursement covers actual sequencing costs, including bioinformatics analysis, data interpretation and clinical reporting.
- ✓ Encourage combined reimbursement policies for NGS-based biomarker testing and targeted therapies to accelerate access to precision medicine.

Invest in infrastructure, workforce training and centralized support

- ✓ Support the development of high-throughput sequencing centers while ensuring decentralized access to NGS technologies.
- ✓ Invest in bioinformatics training programs to address workforce shortages and strengthen local expertise in data analysis and interpretation.
- ✓ Provide dedicated funding for bioinformatics infrastructure and data storage
- ✓ Promote collaborations between high- and low-volume centers to balance NGS availability.

Standardization of NGS practices and bioinformatics workflows

- ✓ Develop pan-European quality standards for NGS data processing, variant interpretation, and clinical reporting to improve reproducibility.
- ✓ Expand accreditation and external quality assessment (EQA) participation to ensure consistency across NGS laboratories.

Improve awareness and stakeholder engagement

- ✓ Increase education and transparency for policymakers and payers on the cost and complexity of NGS implementation.
- ✓ Enhance public and patient awareness initiatives to improve understanding of genomic testing and its role in personalized medicine.

By addressing these challenges, the European Commission can facilitate the standardized, efficient, and equitable adoption of NGS, ensuring that all patients, regardless of location, have access to cutting-edge genomic testing and personalized cancer treatments.

II. Part 2: WP9 & WP10 capacity building report - April 2024

1. Introduction (aims and objectives)

The main objective of the CAN.HEAL initiative is to bridge cancer prevention, diagnosis, and treatment through personalized medicine. It focuses on the pathways to implement next-generation sequencing (NGS) technologies into current practice. Additionally, CAN.HEAL supports the adoption of innovative interventions by disseminating expertise and recommendations on precision medicine, ensuring that technological advancements are effectively integrated into healthcare systems for improved patient outcomes.

As part of task 9.4 from WP9 (treatment and follow-up) and task 10.3 from WP10 (oncology decision support tools (oncDST)), a joint capacity building (CB) exercise was performed to:

1. Evaluate the European expansion of precision oncology through Comprehensive Genomic Profiling (CGP) and Molecular Tumour Boards (MTB).
2. Identify methods for piloting Decision Support Tools (DST) in other European countries.

An expert delegation comprising WP9 and WP10 leaders and the CAN.HEAL coordination team initiated this CB exercise with two active CAN.HEAL partners from Greece and Malta, who expressed interest in participating.

2. Involved centres & participants

Sciensano (BE)

Sciensano is the Belgian scientific public health institute that operates under the authority of the federal minister of Public Health and the federal minister of Agriculture. Sciensano supports human and animal health policies from a One Health perspective. Sciensano was represented by the cancer centre for this specific mission. Reflecting on this mission, the cancer centre is coordinating CAN.HEAL and leading WP10: oncology decision support tools.

Jessa Hospital (BE)

The Jessa Hospital, located in Hasselt, Belgium, is a regional hospital with the characteristics of a university hospital. It serves as a reference hospital, offering a wide range of innovative and high-quality medical services and patient care. Collaborating closely with partner hospitals, Jessa Hospital strives to provide the best possible treatment with a strong emphasis on patient-friendliness and safety. This commitment to excellence ensures that patients receive top-tier care in a supportive and secure environment. Reflecting on this mission, Jessa Hospital is involved in CAN.HEAL as the lead of WP9: treatment and follow-up.

INAB-CERTH (Greece)

The Institute of Applied Biosciences at the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (INAB|CERTH) is the flagship institute for research in Life Sciences in Northern Greece. INAB|CERTH aims to promote basic research while providing solutions to important social needs related to health and well-being. The Molecular Diagnostic Unit (MDU) of INAB-CERTH specialises in providing fast, accurate diagnostic tests. The Unit is constantly researching and developing new molecular diagnostic methods which can be introduced into the clinical practice.

Mater Dei Hospital (Malta)

Mater Dei Hospital (MDH) is the only, state-run, acute general teaching hospital in Malta. It offers a full range of hospital services, both inpatient and outpatient, including an extensive range of specialist services. MDH is also a teaching hospital and collaborates closely with the University of Malta. The Pathology Department at MDH offers an extensive range of services including over 1700 different tests that are carried out at the various MDH laboratories. Other specialized tests are subcontracted to specialised labs overseas. The laboratories include molecular pathology and genetics, haematology (including molecular haematology), cytogenetics, histopathology and cytology and immunology.

Participants

A list of participants in the capacity-building exercise is available in ANNEX 2.

3. Methodology

The methodology applied for this Capacity Building was :

- Identify needs and interests: WP9/WP10 leaders organized online meetings with each participating country to identify specific needs and interests. It was decided that each country would host a visit from the WP9/WP10 delegation. The schedule of online meetings is documented in ANNEX 3.
- Establishing onsite visit agendas: The WP9/WP10 delegation proposed agendas for onsite visits tailored to the requests and objectives of each country. These agendas were reviewed and refined by the respective countries.
- Preparation of presentation materials: Materials were prepared for each topic on the agenda to support discussions during the visit. These materials are listed in ANNEX 4 and available upon request.
- Onsite visits based on the established agendas.

- Evaluation of visits: The visits were evaluated through detailed reporting to assess their effectiveness and gather feedback for improvement.
- Executing a survey on precision oncology implementation across the EU. The results of this survey regarding NGS activities will be integrated in a separate section of the next version of this deliverable report.

4. Materials and visits

Materials:

WP9 & WP10

- NGS implementation in Belgium: This presentation outlines the various efforts and actions Belgium has undertaken to integrate NGS into clinical practice. It highlights the steps taken, including among others establishing the Commission Personalised Medicine (ComPerMed), developing NGS guidelines, regulatory adjustments and setting up an NGS pilot study. All these steps are integrated into the Roadmap that is developed and funded by the Belgian Ministry of Health. This comprehensive approach illustrates Belgium's commitment to advancing precision medicine through NGS technology.
- Belgian PRECISION initiative as set up by the Belgian Society of Medical Oncologists (BSMO) in collaboration with Sciensano and several industrial partners^{2,3}: Concept, Objectives & Challenges / Results from the BALLETT study: The Belgian PRECISION initiative was exemplified using one of its real-world precision oncology studies, the BALLETT study (Belgian Approach of Local Laboratory Extensive Tumor Testing)⁴. The objectives, methodology, achievements and outcomes of the study were illustrated in addition to the beneficial aspects for the patient and the support this kind of set-up brings to the healthcare provider.
- Oncology decision support tool: EU-oncDST concept: this presentation focused on the work developed by WP 10 regarding oncDST. The concept put forward by the CAN.HEAL consortium was deeply elaborated and feedback was collected from the audience.

² Thouvenin J, Van Marcke C, Decoster L, et al. PRECISION: the Belgian molecular profiling program of metastatic cancer for clinical decision and treatment assignment. *ESMO Open*. 2022;7(4):100524. doi:10.1016/j.esmoop.2022.100524

³ BSMO. Precision initiative “Two ongoing comprehensive genomic profiling studies from BSMO: GeNeo and BALLETT.” BSMO. Published June 24, 2021. Accessed June 21, 2024. <https://www.bsмо.be/news/precision-initiative-two-ongoing-comprehensive-genomic-profiling-studies-from-bsmo-geneo-and-ballett/>

⁴ The Belgian Society of Medical Oncology. *A Study to Examine the Clinical Value of Comprehensive Genomic Profiling Performed by Belgian NGS Laboratories: A Belgian Precision Study of the BSMO in Collaboration With the Cancer Centre - Belgian Approach for Local Laboratory Extensive Tumor Testing (BALLETT)*. clinicaltrials.gov; 2021. Accessed January 1, 2024. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT05058937>

- Cancer diagnostics and treatment: The methodology of a shared-risk clinical trial was explained, using the model of the Dutch Drug Rediscovery Protocol study⁵.
- Genomic in public health: Genome of Europe/EDIC/Genomics Dataspace Infrastructure: the various objectives of several EU initiatives were explained.

Greece:

- Bioinformatics activities @ INAB|CERTH: Particular focus on the design of new algorithms and pipelines, including; methods for multi-omics data integration, including annotation and visualization; machine learning and data mining for pattern recognition in large biodata; automating and standardizing computational workflows; and training delivery for Life Sciences with a primary focus on digital and foundational skills in bioinformatics
- INAB-eHealth lab: Particular focus is given to the deployment of symbolic AI (i.e., Knowledge Graphs and ontologies) and non-symbolic AI (i.e., Machine Learning), especially for drug safety purposes, including pharmacogenomics. Furthermore, the eHealth Lab focuses on the secondary use of healthcare data and acts as the national node of the OHDSI community in Greece.
- INAB-Psychology lab: Particular focus is given on the elicitation of the needs of health care professionals with regards to cancer diagnostics and precision medicine; the advice of experts on the education and training needed for oncologists, haematologists and other prospective members of a molecular tumour board; the overview of the literature with regards to communication skills of clinicians explaining cancer diagnostics and delivering news with regards to prognosis or treatment. Future work includes online seminars on the above topics.

Malta:

- The Maltese situation: Current NGS practices (MOLGEN & HAEM); pipeline projects (CGP, MTB); current research & future diagnostic techniques (incl. liquid biopsy)
- The Maltese situation: current experiences & future expectations from clinicians working in the oncological fields

All presentation materials are listed in ANNEX 4 and available upon request.

Visits

Greece:

- When: 3 April 2024
- Where: INAB-CERTH , Thessaloniki
- Visit of the facilities including the:

⁵ DRUP STUDY. Accessed June 21, 2024. <https://drupstudy.nl/>

- Molecular Diagnostic Unit (MDU)
- Genomic Research Unit (GRU)
- Computational Infrastructure
- List of attendees: see ANNEX 5

Malta:

- When: 4 April 2024
- Where: Mater Dei Hospital
- Visit of the facilities including the:
 - Cytogenetics Laboratory
 - Molecular Haematology laboratory
 - Molecular Pathology & Genetics Laboratory (University satellite lab)
- List of attendees: see ANNEX 5
- The Malta visit included attendance at the 2nd National Biomedical Science Conference: Current & Future Perspectives (5-6 April 2024) organised by the Malta Association of Biomedical Scientists (MABS). The results related to “The Belgian Approach of Local Laboratory Extensive Tumor Tested (BALLETT study) were presented by WP9 leader B. Maes as a keynote lecture.

5. Discussion and outcomes

Greece

The recent workshop on capacity building organized in Greece was a resounding success, leaving participants highly impressed and motivated. Attendees commended the expert facilitators for their depth of knowledge and their ability to convey complex scientific concepts clearly and comprehensively. Discussion sections between the presenters and the audience allowed participants to engage directly with the material, participate and share their experiences. Many participants highlighted the well-structured agenda that maintained a steady pace while covering all essential topics. Overall, the workshop received positive reviews for its insightful content, dynamic delivery, and its potential to significantly impact clinical practices and patient outcomes in precision medicine in Greece.

Agenda:

- NGS implementation in Belgium - Brigitte Maes
- Belgian PRECISION initiative: concept, objectives and challenges - Brigitte Maes
- Oncology decision support tool: EU-oncDST concept - Nancy Frédérickx
- Cancer diagnostics and treatment: Shared-risk clinical trial (DRUP model) - Marc Van Den Bulcke
- Genomic in public health: Genome of Europe/EDIC/Genomics Dataspace Infrastructure: Marc Van Den Bulcke

- Presentation of INAB-CERTH labs
 - Laboratory of Bioinformatics
 - e-Health laboratory
 - Health psychology laboratory

Discussion:

- A roadmap to gradually introduce personalised medicine in cancer care such as the Belgian one presented is difficult to transpose to other countries. Several local, constraining factors are in play: health care budget, regulatory and policy barriers, infrastructure and technology, workforce and training, ethical and social issues, evidence-based clinical integration, patient acceptance and awareness, collaborative efforts, logistical challenges, research and development. Addressing these constraints requires a coordinated effort involving policymakers, healthcare providers, researchers, and the broader community to create an enabling environment for the successful implementation of precision oncology in the healthcare system.
- The Belgian Roadmap aimed primarily towards centralization of NGS testing in Belgium by the concept of recognizing “NGS networks”. Nevertheless, more NGS laboratories were established than anticipated. It was discussed how to determine the ideal balance between centralised and de-centralized NGS testing. Balancing centralized NGS labs with local access is crucial for implementing precision oncology, as was exemplified in the BALLETT study. Centralized labs offer resource optimization, high expertise, and cost efficiency but may cause access delays and logistical challenges. Local labs provide timely, personalized care close to the patient and reduce disparities but face higher costs and variable quality.
- The number of genes included in an NGS panel is a strategic decision. Comprehensive panels that test a larger number of genes could increase potential treatment options by identifying a wider range of (potentially) actionable mutations. However, this also raises the likelihood of clinically irrelevant or incidental findings, which may complicate clinical decision-making. Therefore, it is important to maintain a balance by leveraging comprehensive panels to maximize treatment possibilities while minimizing the risk of uncovering unrelated or unexpected genetic information.
- It was discussed that healthcare providers should ensure that the patient's perspective is integral to the process, fostering a more collaborative, transparent, and supportive approach to precision oncology.
- One of the requirements of the Belgian NGS Pilot Study to introduce NGS into the health care system was the creation of a national repository for NGS results. All recognized NGS laboratories were mandated to submit the ‘variant call files’ (VCFs) obtained through routine clinical diagnostics to the Sciensano HealthData NGS database. Although this national, extensive database of NGS results has not yet been utilized for analysis, it is considered a valuable resource that warrants thorough exploration.

- The BALLETT study revealed that in 21% of patients who received a treatment recommendation based on CGP of their tumours, the recommendation was followed by the treating physician. It was acknowledged that this result is in line with similar, large precision oncology projects being conducted in other countries, indicating a consistent pattern of moderate adherence to CGP-based treatment recommendations across different healthcare systems. The reasons for not implementing these recommendations are currently being analyzed and will be addressed in the WP9 deliverables, aiming to provide actionable insights and improve adherence rates.
- The OncDST concept is considered challenging to implement due to the continuous updates required in the underlying knowledge bases. However, it is thought that through collaborative efforts and a focus on developing a unified solution, the system might be feasible. This belief is grounded in the idea that ownership and management by the EU Member States will ensure its success.
- The upcoming Joint Action on Precision Medicine (JA-PM) (under the EU4Health Programme) will enable us to address how to provide treatment and drugs that haven't yet received approval in certain EU nations. By pooling resources and sharing best practices, the Joint Action will facilitate the introduction of new precision medicine treatments, ensuring equitable access to the latest medical advancements for all EU citizens.
- Psychology lab, led by Christina Karamanidou has developed and presented
 - a decision support tool to assist clinicians in evaluating patients' treatment preferences. This tool includes a platform for patients' literacy assessment, conducted before the patient meets with the clinician. By using it, clinicians can better tailor treatment choices to align with the patient's literacy level and expectations, leading to more personalized and effective care. This proactive approach enhances communication and ensures that treatment decisions are made collaboratively, respecting the patient's informed preferences.
 - a patient education website for chronic lymphocytic leukaemia (CLL). The website empowers patients by providing information on how to live with CLL at different stages throughout the disease course. Patients can identify with virtual characters representing these stages, helping them understand their journey with the disease.

Facilities visit:

- The Molecular Diagnostic Unit of INAB has installed and implemented a Quality Management System according to the ELOT EN ISO/IEC 15189:2012 Standard.
- INAB is certified according to ISO/IEC 27001:2013 for its Information Security Management System and according to ISO 22301:2019 for its Business Continuity Management System.
- Diagnostic activity includes 50 samples a week corresponding to 1 NGS run every 2 weeks

- Column-based extraction from various sample types (mainly blood, bone marrow, FFPE sections)
- Various NGS equipment with different sequencing chemistries and large computational unit

Malta

The capacity-building exercise in Malta successfully achieved its aims while showcasing the current and potential capabilities of various molecular testing services. The workshop was attended by healthcare professionals from various disciplines, including oncology, pathology, public health, and management. In addition to dissemination of the highly relevant work being carried out by the CAN.HEAL consortium, it served as a networking event for all attendees. The meetings were very well received by the Maltese participants and generated a lot of enthusiasm that will hopefully be translated into sustainable momentum for change and development.

Technical Meeting A:

Agenda

- NGS implementation in Belgium (roadbook: ComPerMed, NGS convention, reimbursement): Els Van Valckenborgh
- Belgian Precision approach: concept, objectives and challenges – BALLETT study: Brigitte Maes
- The Maltese situation: Current NGS practices (MOLGEN & HAEM); pipeline projects (CGP, MTB); current research & future diagnostic techniques (incl. liquid biopsy)

Discussion

- In Belgium, NGS networks were created with specific criteria, including a minimum of two hospitals and one or more NGS labs. This requirement aimed to keep NGS testing costs affordable. Although the creation of these networks was not optimal, it successfully fostered a strong community with robust interactions among institutions across Belgium. The scientific working groups of the Commission on Personalised Medicine (ComPerMed) also played a significant role in this development. They aimed to harmonize and improve the quality of NGS testing by designing technical and clinical guidelines, further enhancing collaboration and the standardized integration of NGS technology into clinical practice.
- The BALLETT study highlights the benefits of nationwide standardized CGP. By providing consistent and high-quality genomic data, standardized CGP can better inform treatment decisions. Moreover, the follow-up results from the BALLETT study will contribute to a growing body of evidence supporting the clinical utility of CGP. This evidence is crucial for advocating for the future reimbursement of CGP testing, ensuring broader access to advanced precision oncology for patients.

- Access to clinical trials varies significantly between countries and within countries, leading to inequalities as participation often requires the financial ability to travel abroad for extended periods. Malta is seeking support to facilitate the enrolment of its patients in clinical trials. The purpose of a DRUP-like trial was explained by the WP9/WP10 delegation, highlighting its potential to enhance access. This type of trial will be a focal point in the upcoming Joint Action on precision medicine, aiming to improve equity in clinical trial participation and access to innovative treatments.

The following limitations within MDH Laboratories were discussed:

- The primary constraint on expanding the service is an insufficient workforce. For example, currently, there are 6 staff members at the Molecular Pathology & Genetics laboratory, but ideally, 16 are needed. Efforts are underway to attract more personnel and seek international training opportunities to bolster the workforce. This strategic approach aims to enhance service capacity and improve overall efficiency in meeting national healthcare demands.
- Despite approximately 20 individuals graduating annually in lab science locally, nearly all are recruited by the private sector leaving very few available for engagement with the public hospital sector.
- Workforce capacity constraints are also present in other healthcare professional groups including the medical class although the number of qualified specialists in several areas is increasing. However, we are still faced with issues concerned with the retention of specialist expertise in some areas arising from the small overall population leading to limitations in sustained clinical exposure. This becomes more acute with the rarer cancer groups.

Technical Meeting B:

Agenda

- Oncology decision support tool: EU-oncDST concept: Nancy Frédérickx
- Cancer diagnostics and treatment: Shared-risk clinical trial (DRUP) Marc Van den Bulcke
- The Maltese situation: current experiences & future expectations from clinicians working in the oncological fields.

Discussion

- The European oncology decision support tool (EU-oncDST) concept was discussed and presented to the Malta assembly to gather their feedback and input. This concept is intended to harmonize the oncology DST landscape, centralize data, provide structured reporting, and ensure interoperability at the local, national or European level. This will provide clinicians with support in their oncology decision-making. It was clear that for some local professionals, the challenge seemed ambitious. However, it is also clear that an active public contribution seems key for optimal implementation and system ownership that are rapidly evolving commercially.
- Divergent views emerged regarding the future role of artificial intelligence (AI) in the oncDST field. One perspective suggests that AI might replace clinicians and MTBs, while another

argues that AI will assist clinicians and MTBs by gathering and analysing recommendations without replacing them. Ultimately, even with the use of AI models, the decision-making authority should remain with the clinician.

- Concerns were raised about the liability of clinicians if MTB recommendations are not followed. Clinicians have the autonomy to decide what is best for the patient, considering the recommendations as well as the patient's wishes. This ensures that clinical decisions are personalized, not only at the genomic and medical level but also taking into account patient preferences. Ultimately, the clinician's judgment and the patient's input guide the treatment plan, balancing expert recommendations with personal and ethical considerations.

The shared-risk clinical trial model, such as DRUP, is a public-private collaborative research initiative designed to balance innovation funding with risk-sharing between sectors.

- Initial costs are covered by private industry.
- Private partners typically seek reimbursement around phase 3 of the trial, depending on its success.
- The system requires refinement, as patients who do not benefit from the trial have limited alternatives.
- Each country approves and reimburses different sets of drugs, complicating the expansion of this model across the entire EU for all drugs.
- Additionally, enhancing coordination and standardization among EU countries could improve the feasibility and effectiveness of this model, ensuring broader access to innovative treatments while maintaining economic viability.

The local clinical situation in Malta was discussed with several key points:

- Issues with the supply chain related to molecular diagnostics were discussed. There is a need for improved logistics and consistent availability of necessary materials.
- NGS testing is funded by the state, ensuring accessibility for patients without direct financial burden.
- Malta presented a range of studies aimed at optimizing diagnosis and enhancing service quality. These efforts include the validation of an HRD panel (Homologous Recombination Deficiency; IVD certified, Illumina), liquid biopsy techniques, and the development of additional methods for diagnostics of lymphoid neoplasms, minimal residual disease detection in myeloid neoplasms and pediatric oncology. Comprehensive Genomic Profiling (CGP) of solid tumours, ideally with the setting up of a Molecular Tumour Board, is in the pipeline.
- The cytogenetics lab presented its activities related to Fluorescence In Situ Hybridization (FISH) in Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia, demonstrating their efforts in applying state-of-the-art diagnostics for this condition. This work showcases the lab's commitment to utilizing advanced techniques to enhance diagnostic accuracy and improve patient outcomes. The

introduction of Optical Genome Mapping (OGM) to detect cytogenetic abnormalities in cancer cases is in the pipeline. This technology will complement NGS, which has limitations in identifying structural variants (SV) and copy number variations (CNV), both crucial for the accurate diagnosis of sarcomas. Traditional cytogenetic techniques like karyotyping and FISH also have resolution limitations. OGM, a relatively new technology, surpasses these methods by detecting structural variations with greater accuracy. Combining CGP with OGM would provide a more comprehensive genetic profile.

Technical Meeting C:

Agenda

- Genomics in public health: Genome of Europe/EDIC/Genomics Dataspace Infrastructure: Marc Van Den Bulcke

Discussion

European genomic efforts, including the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI), were discussed. Key points included:

- Polygenic risk scores may predict cancer development but do not play a role in diagnosis, highlighting their utility in risk assessment rather than clinical diagnosis.
- Ethical and legal considerations concerning the Genomic Dataspace Infrastructure and its relation to the EHDS were addressed, emphasizing the need for clear regulatory frameworks.
- For whole genome sequencing, local data management, including cataloguing and access permissions will be determined by Malta, ensuring that national policies govern data use.
- Although acquiring data across EU Member States via the updated version of the EHDS will be challenging, the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) is expected to facilitate data acquisition in genomics, improving cross-border research and collaboration.

The EU Joint Action (JA) PreventNCD was discussed.

- This joint action emphasizes social determinants of health rather than solely focusing on preventable risk factors, highlighting the importance of broader social influences on health outcomes.
- Risk is perceived differently across various professional and social backgrounds, with patients, professionals, and policymakers each prioritizing different aspects of health and risk.
- Ms Sarah Pace from the Department of Health Regulation represents Malta in this JA, leveraging the expertise of the already established Social Determinants of Health Unit.
- This initiative underscores the need for a comprehensive approach to health, integrating social, economic, and environmental factors to effectively prevent non-communicable diseases.

New call on Joint action of Precision Medicine (JA-PM):

- Dr. Jeanesse Scerri was recently nominated by MHA to represent Malta in this new personalized cancer medicine project, reflecting Malta's commitment to advancing personalized cancer treatment initiatives.
- JA-PM objectives: Despite significant investments and progress in personalized medicine, translating knowledge into clinical applications and accelerating innovation uptake remains challenging. The Joint action of Precision Medicine will aim to establish a research and innovation (R&I) partnership focused on personalized medicine. This partnership seeks to leverage the characterization of individuals' phenotypes and genotypes to tailor health strategies, thereby improving health outcomes through disease prevention and patient-centred care, by uniting stakeholders, creating synergies, and coordinating R&I actions to facilitate the rapid and effective implementation of personalized medicine across Europe. It will build on existing initiatives, facilitate information exchange, and stimulate innovations to benefit European citizens and industry.

-

The 1+ Million Genomes (1+MG) project was discussed:

- Currently, funding is available for sequencing 50,000 genomes, a reduction from the initial goal of 1 million genomes.
- Malta is actively participation in the 1+MG, Genome of Europe (GoE) and Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) projects.
- Malta is working towards submitting 1,000 whole genome sequences collected through the DWARNA to GoE project.
- By its active participation, Malta is contributing to enhancing genomic research, improving personalized medicine, and fostering collaboration across Europe to leverage genetic data for better healthcare outcomes.

Facilities visit

- Automatic workflow is implemented for the haematological analysis and runs between 200 to 800 samples daily.
- NGS analysis is done by the Oncomine software from Thermofisher.
- Various NGS equipment are available.

6. Conclusion

Both Greece and Malta have various and sufficient NGS infrastructure and expertise in NGS and precision oncology is present. Some issues and action points were identified:

Specifically, Greece has a strong expertise in molecular testing and patient care. However, the lack of health data registration and reimbursement of genetic tests in Greece is hampering the implementation of NGS according to the Belgian roadbook.

In Malta, there is a strong interest in implementing a BALLETT-like study, focusing on the attraction of clinical trials, the integration of Comprehensive Genomic Profiling (CGP) tests into routine practice, and the establishment of Molecular Tumor Boards (MTB). The Life Sciences Park is being developed as a centre for attracting clinical trials. Additionally, the local team is engaged in discussions with the UK to evaluate the advantages of Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) versus Fluorescence In Situ Hybridization (FISH) for testing a proportion of sarcomatous tumours, particularly in younger individuals.

Malta aims to ensure the validation of the CGP test through reports and follow-up meetings, facilitating its use in MTBs for providing recommendations. OGM will further complement NGS techniques for the stratification of solid tumours. There is also a plan to include liquid biopsy in routine diagnostic services, especially for monitoring EGFR T790M in lung adenocarcinoma patients treated with first-generation EGFR TKIs.

However, Malta faces challenges related to an insufficient workforce, and there is a need to attract more Laboratory Scientists each year over the next five years to strengthen genetics and genomics capabilities. The Department of Programme Implementation is exploring EU initiatives to identify further opportunities for application. Finally, Malta is working towards having Mater Dei Hospital/Sir Anthony Mamo Oncology Centre recognized as an official cancer centre within the framework of the Joint Action on Network of Comprehensive Cancer Centres (JA CraNE), and discussions are planned with Luxembourg and Cyprus (other small EU MSs) to address potential challenges related to official recognition for their centres.

7. Action Points

- Marc Van de Bulcke was invited to speak in July at the 1st Cancer Policy Forum held in Athens, Greece.
- In preparation for the upcoming WP 10 deliverable (D10.2, due in October 2024), WP10 requests the support of the Greek and Maltese teams in reviewing it. Their insights and perspectives will be valuable in considering all aspects of implementing this challenging concept.
- The participation of Malta and Greece in the Joint Action (JA) of Precision Medicine will enhance their access to treatment and clinical trials.
- Both Malta and Greece are interested in actively sharing and gaining expertise in NGS analysis.
- Collaboratively, CAN.HEAL has initiated the sequencing of ## Maltese patients with the GoE initiative.
- Malta has been put in contact with CAN.HEAL partners that could support their request for training opportunities. The discussions are ongoing.

ANNEX 1: Survey results on NGS bioinformatics practices in the EU

Location of archived data

- Locally secured server, NAS (n=48; 75.0%)
- Cloud system (n=8; 12.5%)
- External Hard Drive, tape storage (LTO) (n=6; 9.4%)
- Other (n=2; 3.1%)

Duration of archiving

- Undetermined (n=20; 31.2%)
- > 5 years (n=21; 32.8%)
- 2 to 5 years (n=16; 25.0%)
- 12 to 24 months (n=3; 4.7%)
- 3 to 12 months (n=3; 4.7%)
- < 3 months (n=1; 1.6%)

Duration of output file storage

- Undetermined (n=26; 40.6%)
- > 5 years (n=26; 40.6%)
- 2 to 5 years (n=8; 12.5%)
- 12 to 24 months (n=2; 3.1%)
- 3 to 12 months (n=1; 1.6%)
- < 3 months (n=1; 1.6%)

Specific policy regarding raw data sharing for research

- No (n=34; 53.1%)
- Yes (n=30; 46.9%)

ANNEX 2: Capacity visits - participant lists

Name	CAN.HEAL Implication	Organism	Function
Brigitte Maes	WP9 leader	Jessa Hospital	Clinical Pathologist
Els Van Valckenborgh	CAN.HEAL coordinator	Sciensano	Senior Scientist Cancer Centre
Marc Van Den Bulcke	CAN.HEAL coordinator	Sciensano	Head of Cancer Centre
Nancy Frédérickx	WP10 leader	Sciensano	Scientist Cancer Centre
Kostas Stamatopoulos	WP11 co-leader	CERTH	Hematologist, Research Director INAB CERTH
Anastasia Chatzidimitriou	WP11 co-leader	CERTH	Molecular biologist - Geneticist, Director INAB CERTH
Stamatia Laidou	WP11 participant	CERTH	Molecular biologist, Head of MDU INAB CERTH
Christina Karamanidou	WP13 participant	CERTH	Psychologist, Head of Health Psychology lab INAB CERTH
Christina Kakalou	WP13 participant	CERTH	Electrical and Computer Engineer, Member of Health Psychology lab INAB CERTH
Fotis Psomopoulos	WP11 participant	CERTH	Electrical and Computer Engineer, Head of Lab of Bioinformatics INAB CERTH
Pantelis Natsiavas	WP11 participant	CERTH	Electrical and Computer Engineer, Head of e-Health Lab INAB CERTH
George Kapatnakis	WP13 participant	ELLOK	Patient advocate, President, Hellenic Cancer Organization
Maria Theodoridou	WP13 participant	ELLOK	Patient advocate
Maria Nomikou	WP13 participant	ELLOK	Patient advocate
Katerina Nikitara	WP13 participant	ELLOK	Patient advocate
Miriam Dalmas		MHA	
Christian Scerri		MHA	Consultant Geneticist, i/c MOLGEN
Jeanesse Scerri	WP7, 8, 11, 13 participant	MHA	Higher Allied Health Practitioner (MLS), i/c MOLGEN
Jessica Debattista	WP11 participant	MHA	Higher Allied Health Practitioner (MLS)
Charmaine Cordina		MHA	
Michael Debono		MHA	
Karen Muscat		MHA	

ANNEX 3: Capacity building preparatory meetings

Date of the online meetings	Country involved	Note
14/12/2023	Belgium	Internal preliminary meeting
19/01/2024	Belgium - Malta	
24/01/2024	Belgium - Greece	
22/02/2024	Belgium	Internal program validation

ANNEX 4: Materials

WP9/WP10

- NGS implementation in Belgium - Els Van Valckenborgh
- Belgian Precision approach: concept, objectives and challenges - Brigitte Maes
- Oncology decision support tool: EU-oncDST concept - Nancy Frédérickx
- Cancer diagnostics and treatment: Shared-risk clinical trial (DRUP) - Marc Van Den Bulcke
- Genomic in public health: Genome of Europe/EDIC/Genomics Dataspace Infrastructure: Marc Van Den Bulcke

ANNEX 5: List of attendees

Greece

Co-funded by the
European Union

European Commission EU4Health Programme 2021-2027, Grant Agreement Number 101080009

Attendance list

Capacity Building activity within the EU4Health project Can.Heal

CERTH, Thessaloniki, April 3, 2024

A/A	Name	Surname	Organization	Email	Signature
1	Maria	Nomikou	ELLOK	director@ellok.org	
2	Katerina	Nikitara	ELLOK	euprogram@ellok.org	
3	Maria	Theodoridou	ELLOK	maria.theodoridou@ellok.org	
4	Brigitte	Mues	Jena Hospital	Brigitte.Mues@jena2h.de	

Co-funded by the
European Union

European Commission EU4Health Programme 2021-2027, Grant Agreement Number 101080009

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Malta

Attendees at the EU Project - Coordination and Support Action CAN.HEAL - Building the EU cancer and public health genomics platform Member States' visits – Malta, 4th April 2024

Attendee name	Comments/designation	
Dr Marc Van Den Bulcke	CAN.HEAL delegation (4 persons)	
Dr Brigitte Maes		
Dr Nancy Frédérickx		
Dr Els Van Valckenborgh		
Prof Christian Scerri	Local organising team (5 persons)	Consultant Clinical Genetics
Dr Miriam Dalmas		Consultant Public Health Medicine
Dr Jeanesse Scerri		Lead scientist/Molecular Genetics Lab.
Ms Jessica Debattista		Scientist/Molecular Genetics Lab.
Dr Charmaine Cordina		Specialist trainee Public Health Medicine
Participants (36 persons)		
Mr Walter Busuttill	Chief Medical Officer	
Dr Christopher Barbara	Clinical Chair Pathology	
Dr Nick Refalo	Clinical Chair Oncology and Haematology	

Prof David Pace	Clinical Chair Paediatrics
Prof Alex Gatt	Consultant Hematology
Dr David James Camilleri	Consultant Hematology
Dr Nathalie Galea	Consultant Paediatric Oncology
Dr Janabel Said	Consultant Clinical Oncology
Dr Etienne Paris	Consultant Clinical Oncology
Dr Malcolm Buhagiar	Consultant Clinical Oncology
Dr Alexandra Betts	Consultant Histopathology
Dr Jacob Vella	Specialist trainee Clinical Genetics
Dr Nadine De Battista	Specialist trainee Clinical Genetics
Mr Michael Debono	Lead scientist/Haematology Lab.
Ms Karen Muscat	Lead scientist/Cytogenetics Lab.
Dr Graziella Zahra	Lead scientist/Molecular Diagnostics Lab.
Prof Nikola Pace	National node director of BBMRI.mt
Dr Laura Grech	Scientist/Molecular Genetics Lab.
Dr Danika Marmara'	Director, Cancer Care Pathway
Ms Jasmine Gauci	Research Manager, Cancer Care Pathway
Dr Dorianne Farrugia	Consultant Public Health Medicine/representing DG Health Care Services
Dr Jason Attard	Resident Specialist Public Health Medicine/representing DG Health Regulation
Dr Sascha Reiff	Clinical Lead, National Screening Centre
Mr Joseph Debono	Medical Director, Mater Dei Hospital
Dr Beatrice Farrugia	Office of the Medical Director, Mater Dei Hospital
Dr Karen Borg	Office of the Medical Director, Mater Dei Hospital
Mr Euchar Sultana	Chief Information Officer
Dr Ivan Cacciottolo	Office of the Chief Information Officer
Prof Neville Calleja	Director, Health Information and Research
Dr Miriam Azzopardi	Head, National Cancer Registry
Dr Alexia Bezzina	Office of the Chief Medical Officer
Dr Amanda Bugeja	Office of the Chief Medical Officer
Prof David Mamo	Head, Post-Graduate Medical Training Center
Mr Emanuel Gatt	Post-Graduate Medical Training Center
Mr Joseph Abela	Director, Programme Implementation
Mr Andrew Cachia	Office for Programme Implementation